

INFORMATION TECHNOLOGY IN FOREIGN LANGUAGE LESSONS USAGE

Milikov Bakhtiyar

Shahrisabz district, Kashkadarya region

16 - English teacher of a boarding school

Abstract: This article is devoted to the active using of innovative technologies in teaching foreign languages in Uzbekistan.

Key words: foreign language, games, innovative technologies, technical tools, teaching method.

Annotatsiya: Ushbu maqolada O'zbekiston Respublikasida chet tillariga berilgan katta ahamiyat, hamda ularni o'rganish uchun zarur bo'lgan innovatsion texnologiyalar yoritilgan.

Kalit so'zlar: Chet tili, o'yin, innovatsion texnologiya, texnologik vositalar, usullar, metodlar.

Аннотация: В данной статье анализируется активное использование инновационных технологий преподавания иностранных языков в Республике Узбекистан.

Ключевые слова: иностранный язык, игры, инновационные технологии, технологические инструменты, методы преподавания.

In today's rapidly developing age, science and technology are growing rapidly. Progress is being made in every field. In particular, great changes and significant progress are being made in science. Delivery of each subject to students using new innovative technologies is one of the main requirements of today's education. In the process of globalization, it is difficult to imagine our life without the Internet. It is one of the most effective ways to use it effectively in the process of learning and teaching a foreign language. There will be an opportunity to communicate with people who speak a foreign language through the Internet. You can improve writing practice by writing letters via e-mail. Bringing modern communication technologies into the educational process, using them purposefully and correctly, and using them, increasing the student's interest in a foreign language, and increasing the effectiveness of teaching is the most important issue. Through this, the opportunity to use innovative technologies of education will be created and the demand will increase.

Today, there are several different methods of innovative educational technologies. If they use wide and various methods to cover the topic in the lessons, the efficiency of the lesson will be high and the increase of students' interest in the lesson will be ensured. It is intended to increase the effectiveness of education by bringing innovations into the educational process and implementing them. The use of various role-playing, action games in the teaching of foreign language classes increases interest in the lesson and in language learning. By having students work in pairs or small groups, it helps students to communicate with others. The research process used methods of historical, logical, analysis and

synthesis of practical knowledge. In the process of this research, today's importance of using information technology in foreign language lessons was objectively revealed. Today, the stages of teaching Boom's taxonomy are taught in a logical sequence using innovative technologies. The use of graphic organizers in the educational process is one of the most important tools for explaining the topic and delivering it to students. It is also possible to use several different graphic organizers to cover the same topic. When teaching a foreign language, it is appropriate to explain new words and grammatical rules related to the topic using graphic organizers. These are also easier to remember if they are presented through graphic organizers. The effectiveness of using different tables in the process of teaching a foreign language is also high. Using the tables in the educational process, students can learn a certain grammar rule, for example, making sentences using tenses, placing new words. At a time when the need to learn a foreign language is high, effective use of modern information technologies and innovative educational technologies in the educational process makes this process effective. The effectiveness of innovative educational technologies is when they are used correctly and effectively in the educational process.

After our country gained independence, interest in teaching foreign languages increased and many opportunities were created for young people. As our first president Islam Karimov said, "Nowadays, teaching of foreign languages is given great importance in our country. This is certainly not for nothing.

Today, there is no need to overestimate the importance of perfect knowledge of foreign languages for our countries, which are striving to take their rightful place

in the world community, for our people, who are building their great future in solidarity and cooperation with our foreign partners." As a logical continuation of these thoughts, on December 10, 2012 The adopted Presidential Decree "On measures to further improve the system of teaching foreign languages" expanded the opportunities for learning foreign languages. In our republic, new methods and requirements have been developed for teaching a foreign language, in accordance with the recommendations of the pan-European framework for assessing the knowledge and skills of foreign language teachers (CEFR). According to it, textbooks were created for students of general education schools and vocational colleges. In accordance with these requirements, classrooms were equipped with stands and new information and communication techniques. The demand for learning a foreign language is also increasing day by day. Foreign language science is divided into four aspects (reading, speaking, listening comprehension and speaking), and separate concepts and skills are given for each of them. Educational technologies are effective use of modern information technologies in the educational process. It is also intended to increase the quality and efficiency of education by introducing modern innovative technologies into the educational process. In particular, there are several advantages of using such information and communication technologies in learning a foreign language. The role of modern technology in language learning and teaching is immeasurable. The use of technological tools is useful in every aspect of learning a foreign language (reading, writing, listening and speaking). For example, in order to listen and understand, of course, this process cannot be carried out without a computer, player, CD discs. Listening comprehension is one of the most important parts of language learning. At the same time, the reader is required to pay attention to the

speaker's pronunciation, adherence to grammatical rules, vocabulary and its meanings. An important factor in the use of modern technologies in the educational process is that students know and use information and communication technologies well. Teaching and learning a foreign language using modern technologies is one of the most fruitful ways.

In this process, including: - when using computers, the student can watch and listen to foreign language videos, demonstrations, dialogues, movies or cartoons;

- it is possible to listen and watch foreign language radio broadcasts and television programs; - the use of tape recorders and cassettes, which are considered a more traditional method;

- CD players can be used. The use of these technical tools makes the process of learning a foreign language more interesting and effective for students.

Today, teaching through interactive games is becoming a tradition in schools. It is known that the lesson is based on various games, which allows students to demonstrate their abilities, concentrate, improve their knowledge and skills, and become stronger. The basis of the use of game technology is the activity that activates and accelerates the student. According to psychologists, the psychological mechanisms of playful activity rely on the fundamental needs of a person to express himself, find a stable place in life, self-control, and realize his potential. Any game should be based on generally accepted educational principles and tactics. Educational games should be based on educational subjects.

In the process of games, the student is more interested in this activity than in a regular lesson and works freely. It should be noted that the game is, first of all, a method of teaching. Pupils participate in game lessons with interest, strive to win, the teacher also provides education to the pupil through them. The student believes and is interested in playing English games, speaking, listening, and writing. We know that in the current educational process, the student should be the subject. Focusing on more interactive methods will increase the effectiveness of education. One of the most important requirements for English language classes is to teach students to think independently. Today, English language teachers are using the following innovative methods based on the experience of pedagogues from the United States of America and England:

- To apply this method of "Creative Problem Solving", the beginning of the story is read and the conclusion of the story is referred to the judgment of the students;
- "Merry Riddles" teaching riddles to students is important in teaching English, they learn unfamiliar words and find the answer to a riddle;
- "Quick answers" help to improve the efficiency of the lesson;
- "Chigil yazdi" ("Warm-up exercises") using various games in the classroom to interest students in the lesson;
- "Pantomime" (pantomime) this method can be used in a lesson where very difficult topics need to be explained or when written exercises are done and students are tired;
- "A chain story" method helps to develop students' oral speech;

- "Role games" (Acting characters) this method can be used in all types of lessons. In order to teach the profession, people in professions such as "Interpreter", "Translator", "Writer", "Poet" can participate in the class and talk with the students;

As we have seen, each innovative technology has its own advantages. All such methods include cooperation between the teacher and the student, the active action of the student in the educational process.

In conclusion, as a result of using innovative methods in English lessons, students' logical thinking skills develop, their speech becomes fluent, and the ability to answer quickly and correctly is formed. Such methods make students eager for knowledge. The student tries to prepare thoroughly for the lessons. This makes students active subjects of the educational process. As the educational system sets itself the task of educating a free-thinking, well-rounded, mature person, in the future, we future teachers will contribute by developing ways to effectively use innovative technologies.

Foydalanilgan adabiyotlar:

1. Bekmuratova U. B. Abstract on "Using innovative technologies in teaching English". Tashkent - 2012
2. Otao'ba, M. P. Use of modern innovative technologies in foreign language teaching and its effectiveness / M. P. Otao'ba.

3. N. Q. Khatamova, M. N. Mirzayeva. "INTERACTIVE METHODS USED IN ENGLISH LANGUAGE LESSONS" (methodical guide), Navoi, 2006, 40 pages.
4. M. Kholdorova, N. Fayziyeva, F. Rikhsittilayeva. "USING HELPFUL TOOLS IN FOREIGN LANGUAGE TEACHING". Tashkent: TDPU named after Nizomi, 2005
5. O'Hoshimov, I. Yakubov. "ENGLISH TEACHING METHODOLOGY" (study guide) Tashkent: "Sharq" publishing house, 2003